

Emotional Driving Experiences: an Opportunity for Future Technology

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Abstract:

The paper focuses on the emotional aspect of the driving experience. An experiment studying emotions during interaction between driver and vehicle interface in a natural driving situation was conducted. The aim was to identify aspects that affected the driving experience in a positive or negative manner. A triangulation method comprising interviews, observations and think-aloud protocols were used. Participants were required to drive around a specified route while interacting with the vehicle interface. They were interviewed before and after driving to identify their emotional state. During the drive they were asked to perform particular tasks with the interface as well as conduct a think-aloud protocol about their emotions while performing the tasks.

Findings showed that emotions during interaction in low-traffic contexts did not impact the overall experience, while emotions elicited in high-traffic context influenced the overall emotional experience perceived. In addition, drivers in a positive emotional state before driving that experienced challenging interactions in high-traffic context perceived the overall experience as negative. Surprisingly, drivers in a negative emotional state prior to driving that experienced and overcame challenging interactions in high-traffic contexts perceived the overall experience as positive. An additional finding revealed that extended visual interaction with the vehicle interface in high-traffic situations led to negative emotions. The paper concludes by outlining future directions and suggestions as to how current and upcoming technology such as context aware interfaces, digital interfaces, and interfaces utilising smart materials may be applied to vehicle interiors to help support positive (and avoid negative) emotional experiences in a variety of contexts.

Keywords: Design and Emotion, Driving and Emotions, Vehicle Interface Design, Intelligent interfaces

1. Introduction

The activity of driving requires the involvement of a variety of human resources. For instance, to drive a vehicle on a busy city road effectively and safely, drivers must coordinate their cognitive capabilities, physical abilities and emotions simultaneously. If one of these is affected, it will invariably influence the others, as a result affecting the driving experience.

Throughout the driving activity, drivers simultaneously interact with the vehicle's interface including radio, air-condition and other on-board equipment. There is limited available literature studying the emotional experience of driving and interacting with the vehicle interface, and how to approach the design of vehicle interfaces in order to support positive (and avoid negative) overall emotional experiences during interactions. This is an important area of research as the emotional state, or mood, of the driver will affect the effectiveness, safety and overall satisfaction of the driving activity (Mesken, 2001, Nasoz, Ozyer, Lisetti, & Finkelstein, 2002).

This paper presents results from an experiment investigating the *emotional* component of the driving experience during interaction with the vehicle interface while driving. Some of these findings have already been reported in previous papers (Gomez, Popovic, & Bucolo, 2004a, Gomez, Popovic, & Bucolo, 2004b). The current paper expands on these findings and discusses how designers can utilise future technology such as context aware technologies, adaptive interfaces, digital screen technology and ubiquitous computing, within vehicle interface design to support positive emotional experiences in various traffic contexts.

2. The Activity of Driving

Driving requires the management of various human capabilities while focusing on the surrounding environment. As a result, to drive effectively people need to feel comfortable physically, mentally and emotionally. If drivers are at ease they can concentrate, make decisions and judgements successfully and enjoy a positive driving experience. The immediate driver-vehicle interface consisting of equipment like the radio or controls located around the steering wheel is where the application of appropriate design can facilitate comfortable, relaxed, safe and

enjoyable driving. The inclusion of existing and up-and-coming technology in the design of the driver-vehicle interface should not only be ergonomically correct and useable in a physical and cognitive manner but also inspire confidence and make the driver feel emotionally at ease while driving.

2.1 Overall Experience Framework

Within the driving activity, developing an understanding of the interaction between driver, vehicle interface, and context is important. To do this an *overall experience* framework (Figure 1) (Gomez, et al., 2004a) was developed. It is based on the activity theory construct (Nardi, 1996) which stands on the premise that objects are mediators of human experience (Kuutti, 1996). The importance of emotions and context involved during interactions with artefacts or environments is also highlighted within activity theory.

Figure 1, Human-Artefact-Activity within context forms an overall experience.

An overall experience (Figure 1) is composed of the interaction between human and artefact in conjunction with the activity being performed within a particular environmental context. The surrounding environmental context, in which the human-artefact interaction is situated, forms a critical component of the overall experience. If environmental context is not considered within a framework of interaction the intention and meaning behind the activity can easily be misunderstood.

2.2 Framework for the Driving Activity

The driving activity can now be situated as an overall experience within the suggested framework. It consists of two interrelated interaction contexts; the micro-level and macro-level contexts. The micro-level consists of interactions between driver and vehicle (Figure 2, left) and the macro-level consists of interaction between driver-vehicle and external environment (Figure 2, right).

Figure 2, Micro (left) and macro (right) interaction levels for the overall driving experience

To understand the overall driving experience, it is important to consider both interaction contexts in which the driver is simultaneously interacting with. The surrounding environment within the macro-level context (Figure 2, right) is in constant change while driving and as such it is essential to realise that the design of the vehicle interface needs to support these different driving conditions. In this way the physical design of the vehicle interface becomes a mediator for the overall experience attained by the driver.

2.2 Emotions and Experiences

A positive state of mind while driving comes about when the driver is feeling content and relaxed. As mentioned previously, to achieve this, the driver must be physically, cognitively and emotionally comfortable while interacting with the vehicle interface. These capabilities needed for driving are intertwined and influence one another. For example, if drivers are using text

messaging on their mobile phone as they drive their capacity to control their physical skills in an emergency decreases. Alternatively, if drivers are in a negative emotional state, their ability to concentrate or adapt in a critical situation may be affected.

Research has been conducted into the physical and cognitive aspects of driving. For instance, the ergonomic aspects of the vehicle interface has been investigated (Andreoni, Santambrogio, Rabuffetti, & Pedotti, 2002, Lansdown, Brook-Carter, & Kersloot, 2004, Regan, Oxley, Godley, & Tingvall, 2000), resulting in data concerning the physical layout of the vehicle's equipment. There is ongoing research into the cognitive aspects of interactions while driving in respect to concentration and critical decision making while using mobile phones (Schneider & Kiesler, 2005, Strayer & Johnson, 2001). However, there is little available research on the *emotional* aspects of interacting with the vehicle's interface and how this impacts the driving experience, especially how to design for positive emotional experiences during human-vehicle interactions (Mesken, 2001, Mesken, 2003). Emotions are critical components that will impact on the overall experience attained by the driver, influencing all the aspects of the driving activity. They have been shown to directly affect concentration, judgements, decision-making and other critical cognitive and behavioural processes (Frijda, 1986, Picard, 1997, Plutchik, 2003).

Russell's (2003) model of Core Affect was utilised to identify emotions within the context of this research. An explanation of this model has already been reported (Gomez, et al., 2004a, Gomez, et al., 2004b) and a brief outline will suffice in this instance. Russell suggests that a way to categorise emotions is to understand them as a blend of two dimensions. The first is a measure of feeling, ranging from contentment to discontentment (happy to unhappy) while the second is a measure of energy, ranging from excitement to calmness. The intensity of the emotion can be classified as neutral, moderate or extreme. The model of Core Affect (Russell, 2003) was used as a foundation to develop the Emotional Chart (Figure 3) (Gomez, et al., 2004a).

Figure 3, Emotional Chart (after Russell, 2003)

The Emotional Chart composes two hemispheres with ‘positive’ emotions situated on the right and ‘negative’ emotions on the left. To illustrate, the emotion *annoyed*, would be somewhere between ‘neutral’ (midpoint) and ‘unhappy excited’ as depicted on figure 3.

3. Experiment: Exploring the Emotional Driving Experience

An experiment was conducted exploring the aspects that influence the emotional experience within a driving situation. Results from the experiment provide data to better understand how to appropriately apply current and future technologies to vehicle interiors and interfaces so as to support positive emotional (and avoid negative emotional) experiences. Details of this experiment have been presented elsewhere (Gomez, et al., 2004a). The methodology and analysis will be briefly described followed by the main findings.

The study utilised a triangulation approach (Denzin, 1989) consisting of interviews, observation and think-aloud protocol. The advantage of using this approach was that every activity could be verified using each techniques (observation, interviews and think-aloud protocols). In addition, others researchers recommend utilising this type of combination of methodologies for measuring emotions in driving situations (Mesken, 2001).

The experiment focused on a daytime city-driving context. Fifteen participants, all full time staff members at Queensland University of Technology (QUT), were involved in the study. The experiment required each participant to drive a specified route around the central business district of Brisbane. The route consisted of a low, medium, and a high traffic zone. All participants drove in Toyota vehicles and were required to interact with the interface during the drive.

Before driving, participants took part in initial interviews that were aimed at identifying their emotional state prior to driving. During the journey, participants were asked to perform specific tasks like turning on the radio, tuning to a specific radio station, turning on the CD player, using the windscreen wipers and other interactions with the vehicle interface (Gomez, et al., 2004a). At the same time they were asked to verbally express how they were feeling as they performed each task. During the drive, their activities were recorded using a mini DV camera and tripod located on the back seat. In addition, a web-cam was located on the dashboard, used to videotape the participants' facial expressions. When they had completed the drive a retrospective interview regarding their emotional state was conducted. Questions were also asked regarding their emotions about each of the activities performed while driving. The Emotional Chart (Figure 3) was used in the study and formed part of the questions during the interviews.

The experiments were set up to measure the emotional response by analysing participants' facial, vocal and bodily expressions in conjunction with their verbal descriptions of their feelings. Data was coded utilising a software program called The Observer (v.5). This allowed the researcher to code relevant elements of the driving experience and analyse them. The coding system used was split into three categories called *Behavioural Classes* that comprised: Context, Activities and Emotions. Each *Behavioural Class* was broken into *Behaviours*, used to define the categories into more detail.

Context was divided into:

- Low
- Medium
- High

Activities were divided into:

- Correct interaction (coded when participant made no mistakes with a particular task)
- Incorrect interaction (coded when participant made a mistake with a particular task)
- Visual interaction (coded when participant was only looking at the interface rather than physically interacting with it)
- Driving (coded when no other activity was occurring)

Emotions were divided into the same labels as the segments on the Emotional Chart (Figure 3):

- Neutral excited
- Happy excited
- Happy
- Happy calm
- Neutral calm
- Unhappy calm
- Unhappy
- Unhappy excited

At any time throughout the analysis the researcher could code the *Behavioural Class* (context, activity and emotion) and its corresponding *Behaviour*. This resulted in information that was both detailed and comprehensive. With this type of information the software was able to construct a *time-event table* and *time-event plot*, which depicted the coded information in a table and plot format (Table 1). For example consider an instance where a driver is attempting to turn the radio on in high-traffic context. The driver looks at the interface for a few seconds concentrating to find the “on” button. A few seconds later the driver finds the button and turns the radio on, expressing satisfaction as the music begins to play. Table 1 depicts an example of coding for this sequence.

Table 1, Segment of time-event table and corresponding segment of time-event plot

The top portion of table 1 illustrates (from left to right) the start time of a code, the behavioural class, its corresponding behaviour, the end time, and the overall time duration of the code. The corresponding image is a time-event plot of the same information. It illustrates the context (top bar) activities (middle bar) and emotions (bottom bar) in different coloured segments along a timeline (in seconds). In the activities timeline the grey represents driving, light blue represent visual interaction and purple represents correct interaction. In the emotions timeline white represents neutral calm, red represents neutral excited and orange represents happy excited. The time-event table and time-event plots were used to analyse how emotions and interactions in different contexts affected the overall driving experience (Gomez, et al., 2004b).

4. Findings

Three main findings in respect to the emotional experience of driving are outlined. First of all traffic context was found to be of critical importance when exploring the overall emotional experience attained by the user. Second, the driver’s emotional state before driving had an impact on the emotional experience perceived by the user. Third, analysis suggests that extensive visual

interaction with the interface in high traffic context often leads to negative emotions while driving. The first two findings will be briefly outlined as they have previously been presented (Gomez, et al., 2004a, Gomez, et al., 2004b), while the third finding will be discussed in more detail.

The findings support the idea that there exists a micro and macro level of interaction between driver-vehicle interface (Figure 2, left) and driver-vehicle and surrounding environment (Figure 2, right). At the micro-level, emotions experienced by the drivers while interacting with the interface fluctuated throughout the drive, however, the findings suggest that they did not determine their overall emotional experience. The *traffic context* in which the emotions were elicited had a critical impact on the overall emotional experience attained by the driver (Gomez, et al., 2004b). The context thus became the critical component in determining the overall emotional experience. In low-traffic contexts, emotions experienced while interacting with the interface did not influence the overall experience and were not remembered after the drive. In high-traffic context, emotions experienced appeared to be magnified and influenced the overall emotional experience to a great extent. Participants particularly remembered any negative emotions experienced in high-traffic contexts.

Another finding suggests that the emotional state of the driver before driving influenced the overall emotional experience (Gomez, et al., 2004a). Drivers in a positive emotional state before driving who experienced challenging interactions in a high-traffic context perceived the overall experience as negative. Drivers in a negative emotional state before driving, able to overcome challenging interactions in high-traffic contexts, perceived the overall experience as positive. This finding suggests in high-traffic contexts feelings of achievement and accomplishment associated with overcoming challenging interactions help drivers in a negative emotional state perceive overall positive experiences.

An additional finding suggests that extensive visual interaction with the vehicle interface in high-traffic contexts often results in negative emotions. Figures 4 and 5 show a consecutive set of still images of participants 13 and 14 respectively during interaction with the vehicle interface in high-traffic context. In each of the examples the participant is looking at the vehicle interface for

an extended period of time trying to work out how to perform a particular task. As illustrated, the facial expression demonstrates the negative emotions experienced.

Figure 4 shows participant 13 trying to adjust the air-conditioning in high-traffic context. The left image shows the participant looking at the vehicle interface in high-traffic context experiencing concentration. Five seconds later (middle image), the participant is still looking at the vehicle interface but her emotions have become one of annoyance and irritation as she tries to figure out how to perform the task. Four seconds after (right image), the participant has worked out how to perform the task but is still exhibiting negative emotions associated with the extended visual interaction. When asked about this particular task during the retrospective interview participant 13 commented on the problems encountered:

“...Can’t see marker on open-close control, did not realise the air-condition light was off until later... was not bright enough (referring to the air-condition light indicator)”

Figure 4, Still-images of participant 13 experiencing negative emotions after prolonged visual interaction with the air-conditioning system

Figure 5 illustrates participant 14 attempting to turn on the back windscreen wipers in high-traffic context. The first image (left image) shows the participant looking at the vehicle interface in high-traffic context. A few seconds after (middle image) the participant is still focusing on the vehicle interface expressing more intense emotion of confusion and irritation as she tries to figure out how to perform the task. Four seconds later (right image) the participant has not worked out

how to perform the task and continues to express negative emotions associated with the extended visual interaction. The participant also commented on the problems experienced in the retrospective interview:

“...Annoying cause it’s hard to do. Did turn it [on] but only water came on, expected the wipers to come on as well except it didn’t work like the front one (referring to front windscreen wipers)”

Figure 5, Still-images of participant 14 experiencing negative emotions after prolonged visual interaction with the windscreen wiper controls

The examples illustrate how extended visual interaction with vehicle interface can lead to negative emotions while driving. This occurs most significantly in high-traffic contexts. The implication of this finding in regards to the design of vehicle interiors is discussed in section 5.

5. Discussion

How do the results influence the design of vehicle interfaces, and how can the application of current and future technologies support positive emotional experiences? To begin with, the main points identified from the findings were:

- Emotions experienced during interaction with vehicle interface in low-traffic context do not affect the overall experience perceived by the driver.

- Emotions experienced during interaction with vehicle interface in high-traffic context are critical in forming the overall emotional experience attained by the driver.
- The emotional state of the driver before driving will influence the perception of the overall emotional experience of driving. Challenging interactions in high-traffic contexts, under certain conditions, can lead to positive emotional experiences.
- Extended visual interaction with the vehicle interface in high-traffic contexts can lead to negative emotions while driving.

These findings suggest that technology in vehicle interfaces could be applied to support positive emotional experiences in a variety of ways. Some directions include:

- Vehicle interfaces may encourage interaction within a low traffic context, as the emotions experienced in this context will not critically affect the overall experience perceived by the driver. Additionally, rather than being static, the element of fun could be introduced by presenting a variety of ways to interact with the interface.
- If the driver is in a positive mood prior to driving vehicle interfaces may discourage unnecessary interaction within a high-traffic situation since any negative emotions elicited in a high traffic context will impact negatively on the overall emotional experience perceived by the driver.
- If the driver is in a negative mood before driving, vehicle interfaces may encourage certain interactions within a high traffic context since positive emotions associated with overcoming challenging interactions will elicit positive overall emotional experiences.
- In high-traffic contexts, the interface may adapt and discourage unnecessary extended *visual* interaction. In doing so, it will decrease the chances of eliciting negative emotions.

From these findings, the implications for design are that vehicle interfaces should be able to adapt according to the context as well as take into account the emotional state of drivers prior to driving. This may be achieved by designing vehicles with context-aware interfaces as well as vehicle interiors that are sensitive to the emotional state of the driver before and during driving. These technologies would allow the vehicle to adapt appropriately according to the surrounding environment in a dynamic manner so as to enhance the overall driving experience; however there is always the need for the driver to be in control of these systems at any given time.

5.1 Application of Future Technologies

Ubiquitous, embedded or ambient technologies could be applied within interior vehicle designs to make interfaces aware of their surrounding context as well as interiors sensitive to the emotional state of drivers. Digital screens as well as smart materials could be used as adaptable interfaces between the driver and vehicle.

Currently, digital screens are used in vehicle interiors. However, they could be designed in such a way so as to adapt to different surrounding context or user inputs. Navigation systems are a simple example of digital screen technology that responds to its changing surrounding. Within the context of this paper another way digital touch screens could be applied is in the design of the entire centre console (including radio and CD, air-condition, navigation, speedometer or fuel gauge) whereby the entire interface including colour, shape, sensitivity, sound, form of buttons and other features could change and adapt depending on the surrounding context. There is evidence to suggest that this type of technology is already being considered by major car manufacturers for implementation in future vehicles thus enhancing the safety and enjoyment for the driver (Walker, Stanton, & Young, 2001). Essentially the benefit of digital screens is that they would allow for customisation by the driver or other passengers in the vehicle, as well as permit the vehicle itself to utilise context-aware technologies to inform the digital screen how to adapt in different situations.

Smart materials are another type of technology that could be utilised within vehicle interiors. The term 'smart' refers to materials such as thermochromic materials, shape memory alloys and

polymers, and electro-rheological fluids (Friend & Thorpe, 1999). These materials have the ability to change and adapt dynamically to its environment. They offer versatility depending on the surrounding environment, as well as adaptability to the driver's wishes. For example, there are polymers that are able to change dynamically to respond to different stimuli, changing from a high level of stiffness to a low level of stiffness depending on the circumstances. Also, there is ongoing experimentation on conformable elastic materials that can change shape, adapting to the users grip or force applied (Friend & Thorpe, 2003). These materials could be utilised on steering wheels, buttons, control knobs, paddle shifts and other areas of the vehicle interface to enhance comfort and enjoyment in different situations.

Technology also exists to develop interiors that are sensitive to the emotional state of the driver (Nasoz, et al., 2002, Teller, 2004). Sensitive in this case, does not imply that the interface can identify a specific emotion; nevertheless, identifying whether a driver is in a negative or a positive mood is possible. However, at this point in time, the technology to achieve this is still at an early stage of development as is too intrusive to be implemented in a suitable manner.

6. Conclusion

To drive a vehicle safely and effectively and to create a sense of enjoyment within the driving activity, the driver needs to be physically, mentally and emotionally comfortable.

This paper presented an experiment conducted which specifically focused on the emotional aspect of the driving activity within a daytime inner-city driving situation. The findings from this experiment suggest that the surrounding context as well as the driver's emotional state before driving have a major impact on the overall emotional experience attained by the driver. In addition, extended visual interactions with the vehicle interface while driving often lead to negative emotions. These findings help to inform designers as to how to implement current and future technology to vehicle interfaces to support positive emotional experiences during interaction while driving.

The application of context aware technologies, such as ubiquitous and embedded technology as well as technologies that are sensitive to the emotional condition of the driver will allow for the flexibility needed in vehicle interfaces to support positive (and avoid negative) emotional experiences in the driving activity. It is important to consider the application of these technologies into vehicle interface designs as the emotional condition of the driver will affect the overall performance, safety and enjoyment of the driving activity.

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